

The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Task Complexity on the Personal Value of Millennial Workers Internet Service Provider Batam Indonesia through Continuous Commitment in Batam City

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Abstract

The personal values of millennial workers are unique with high self-confidence, focus on achievement, enjoy working in teams, needing a balance between life and work, liking a flexible work environment, and prioritizing job satisfaction. Millennial worker job satisfaction is measured by salary, promotions, supervision from superiors, co-workers, and the job itself with the characteristics of working competent, rigid, responsive to technology, and having low loyalty and commitment. This study examines and analyzes the effect of job satisfaction and task complexity on the personal value of millennial workers by intervening in continuous commitment. This research method is quantitative with a sequential explanatory design; the data were collected through a questionnaire using the Linkert scale, with 100 millennial respondents from ISP companies. Data analysis used Structural Equation Model with innovative, intelligent Partial Least Square software. The study results show that job satisfaction significantly affects millennial workers' values and has no significant impact on continuous commitment intervention. Task complexity significantly affects the personal significance of millennial workers, both directly and by intervening with constant commitment. Meanwhile continuous commitment has no significant direct effect on the unique value of millennial workers. They are testing the structural model of the influence of job satisfaction and task complexity on the personal values of millennial workers. From the results of this study, it is suggested that variables with no significant effect can be increased by holding enlightenment for millennial workers.

Keywords: *Job Satisfaction, Task Complexity, Millennial Worker, Personal Value, Continuous Commitment*

1. INTRODUCTION

Personal individual millennial workers have characteristics that become predictors, one of which is the role of the value system, namely how personal values possessed by individual millennial workers influence their attitudes towards objects and situations (Whitley & Kite, 2010). Value can be conceptualized as a goal or a desired or necessary way of acting. Values have an essential influence on planning and decision-making, how individuals interpret situations and influence thinking and actions in various ways (Rokeach, 1973; Feather, 1975, 2005; Schwartz 1992, 1996 in Feather & Mckee, 2008).

Millennial workers are workers born between the 1980s and 2000s. Millennial workers are gradually replacing worker X; workers are human resources in the organization. Millennial workers will then become leaders who will determine company performance. Millennial

workers have distinctive characteristics influencing how managers and organizations interact and manage their work attitudes and behaviors. The characteristics of millennial workers are more concerned with a personal focus, having abilities, and habits of using life with information technology (Weber, 2017). Millennial workers are individuals who have global insights. This is also believed by the Batam Indonesia Internet service provider (ISP) company. Internet service provider (ISP), Internet Service provider company is a company or business entity that sells Internet or similar connections to customers.

Based on research (Jobplanet, 2017), the gap phenomenon in Indonesia found that the millennial generation (Generation Y) is less loyal to their work. As many as 76.7% of them only lasted 1-2 years at their workplace before deciding to change jobs. Only 9.5% stay in one place for five years or more. Most millennial workers only stay at work for 1–2 years. Most of them are mainly Millennial workers aged 21–25 years. Millennial workers in this age range can be said to have recently entered the workforce. Regarding performance, Millennial workers focus on learning new things, are hard workers, quickly get job satisfaction, can do complex work simultaneously, and enrich their experience.

Jobplanet's research results support previous studies on Millennial employee loyalty to their jobs. Even though millennial workers can be said to be 'disloyal,' that does not always mean it is not good; they always want to learn, are hungry for challenges, and have unique personality values. The gap occurred in ISP (Internet service provider) companies in Batam, Indonesia, where more than 84.8% of workers are millennials. Therefore the ISP company faces millennial generation workers as the generation that dominates the current work environment, where millennial workers have characteristics of being disloyal/low loyalty to the company. Hence, employee turnover often occurs, even still at the training stage. Employee turnover rate (*turnover rate*) is a characteristic of employees having continuous commitment and low loyalty; this is one of the aspects that ISP companies must pay attention to. Companies with *high turnover rates* level will hurt the achievement of company performance.

This study uses a quantitative method with a sequential explanatory design; each variable is described in the form of a questionnaire distributed to millennial ISP Batam Indonesia workers using the simple random sampling method, and the collected data is processed using the Structural Equation Model using bright software Partial Least Square (PLS).

The research results are expected to be able to see the personal value of millennial workers in Internet service provider companies in Batam, Indonesia, when influenced by job satisfaction, task complexity with intervening continuous commitment so that companies can adapt work patterns to the characteristics millennials to be able to achieve maximum company performance targets.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a person's pleasure in his role and work in an organization. The level of individual satisfaction that they get rewarded relatively from various aspects of the work situation of the organization where they work. So job satisfaction concerns the psychology of the individual in the organization caused by the circumstances he feels from his environment (Ancient, 2020). Davis and Newstrom (1985:105) describe "job satisfaction as a set of employee feelings about whether or not their job is fun."

According to Kreitner and Kinicki (2010), job satisfaction is "an affective or emotional response to various aspects of work." According to Robbins (2003: 78), job satisfaction is "a general attitude towards a person's work which shows the difference between the number of rewards the job receives and the amount they believe they should receive." Job satisfaction is a practical or emotional response to various aspects or aspects of one's work, so job satisfaction is not a single concept. A person may be relatively satisfied with one aspect of a job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects (Ardiani, 2017). Job satisfaction is a (positive) attitude of workers towards their work that arises based on an assessment of the work situation. This assessment can be carried out on one of his jobs; the assessment is carried out as a sense of appreciation for achieving one of the essential values in work. Satisfied employees prefer the work situation rather than dislike it. This variable of job satisfaction has been studied by many previous researchers, including: (Setioningtyas & Dyatmika, 2020), And (Nur, 2013),

(Steve M. Jex, 2002) Job satisfaction is "the level of a worker's positive affection towards work and work situations." For Jex, job satisfaction is solely related to the attitude of workers towards their work. This attitude takes place in the cognitive and behavioral aspects. The cognitive aspect of job satisfaction is workers' beliefs about work and work situations: Workers believe that their work is interesting, stimulating, dull, or demanding. The behavioral aspect of work is the tendency of workers' behavior towards their work which is shown through the work done, continuing to stay in their position, or working regularly and disciplined. Barbara, A. Fritzsche and Tiffany J. Parris (2005) define job satisfaction as "an affective variable that results from one's work experience.

a) Factors in job satisfaction

The satisfaction of each employee has a different level because the influencing factors can also vary. For example, some individuals are satisfied because of the amount of salary, but other individuals are satisfied because of the work environment. According to Kreitner and Kinicki, states that job satisfaction is the effectiveness or emotional response to various aspects of work. This definition implies that job satisfaction is not a single concept; instead, a person can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of his work and dissatisfied with one or several other aspects.

Factors that give job satisfaction, according to Blum, are as follows: individual actors, including age, health, character, and expectations

2.2. Task Complexity

Task complexity could be more structured, apparent, and problematic (Sanusi & Iskandar, 2007). The complexity of the task in this study is defined as a task consisting of many different and interrelated parts. (Cecilia Engko, 2007). Task complexity is the number and variety of tasks that make the task complex and confusing, accompanied by limited ability or expertise in completing the task. (Nuarsih & Mertha, 2017)

2.3. Continuous Commitment

Commitment is a relatively stable attitude defined as a strong belief and acceptance of organizational values and goals, a willingness to use all resources for the organization's benefit, and a strong desire to remain a member. Commitment can be defined as the strength of an individual's identification and involvement with the organization. High commitment is characterized by three things, namely strong trust and acceptance of organizational goals and values, a strong will to work for the organization, and the third is a strong desire to remain a

member of the organization (Meyer and Allen in Nortcraft and Neale, 1990, Steers in Dessler, 1994).

Continuity arises when individuals realize that their accumulated investment will be lost if they leave the organization (side bets) or realize there are limited alternatives comparable to their current organization. Hence, individuals need an organization (need). Potential antecedents of this component include age, length of service, and intention to leave the organization (Ery et al., 2021).

2.4 Personal Value of Millennial Workers

The millennial generation is a generation that was born with the rapid development of technology, giving birth to different characteristics compared to other generations. The characteristics of the millennial generation can be described through their values, personality traits, and needs, as expressed by Wexley and Yukl. The millennial generation has values that are believed to be guidelines for action. The millennial generation has specific characteristics that raise certain expectations in the world of work, including job satisfaction.

Expectations are the beliefs or beliefs of an individual regarding things that should happen under certain conditions (Azmi et al., 2021).

3. METHODOLOGY

This research methodology is quantitative research with a descriptive and associative approach. The sampling technique uses non-probability sampling with a saturated sampling method (census). The sample of this research is 100 millennial employees of the Batam Indonesia Internet service provider company. The data used are primary data, with data collection techniques using questionnaires. The data analysis technique uses path analysis using the Smart PLS software data analysis tool.

3.1. Framework

Figure 1: Research Model

From the framework above, the following hypothesis can be made:

- H1: Job satisfaction affects the personal value of millennial workers.
- H2: Tasks Complexity affects the personal values of millennial workers
- H3: Job satisfaction affects the Continuous Commitment of Millennial workers
- H4: Tasks Complexity affects the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers

- H5: Continuous Commitment affects the personal values of millennial workers.
- H6: Job satisfaction affects the personal value of millennial workers by intervening in Continuous Commitment.
- H7: Tasks Complexcity affects the personal value of millennial workers by intervening in Continuous Commitment

4. RESULT SAND FINDINGS

The results of data processing can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 2: Hypothesis Testing Results Framework

From the picture above, a table of research results can be made as follows:

Table 1: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Variable Relations	Path Coefficient	T Value	P-Values	Information
Job Satisfaction → Personal Value Millennial Workers	0.227	2,647	0.007	Significant
Task Complexity → Personal Value Millennial Workers	0.504	4,724	0.000	Significant
Job Satisfaction → Continuous Commitment	0.147	1870	0.058	Not Significant
Task Complexity → Continuous Commitment	0.600	8,594	0.000	Significant
Continuous commitment → Personal Value, Millennial Workers	0.090	1,807	0.421	Not Significant
Job Satisfaction → Continuous Commitment → Personal Value Millennial Workers	0.013	0.643	0.520	Not Significant
Task Complexity → Continuous Commitment → Personal Value Millennial Workers	0.054	0.776	0.438	Not Significant

From the test table above, job satisfaction has a significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers, with a Path Coefficient value of 0.227 at a T-value of 2.647, greater than the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.007. Thus the hypothesis states that there is a direct effect of Job satisfaction on personal value. Millennial workers are accepted (H1) accepted. For testing Task Complexity on the personal values of millennial workers, it also has a significant effect, with a Path Coefficient value of 0.504 at a T-value of 4.724, greater than the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.000. Thus the hypothesis states that there is a direct effect of Task Complexity influence on the personal value of millennial workers is acceptable (H2) is accepted. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers with a Path Coefficient value of 0.147 at a T-value of 1.870, smaller than the standard t-table of 1.96, and a P-Value of 0.058. Thus, the hypothesis that job satisfaction has a direct effect on Continius Millennial workers' commitment is unacceptable (H3) and is rejected. There is a significant influence for the Task Complexity on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, with a Path Coefficient value of 0.6 at a T-value of 8.594 which is large from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.000. Thus, the hypothesis states that Task Complexity's direct effect on Millennial workers' Continuous Commitment (H4) is accepted. There is no significant effect for Continuous Commitment to the personal values of millennial workers, with a Path Coefficient value of 0.09 at a T-value of 1.807 which is small from the standard t-table of 1.96, and a P-Value of 0.421. Thus the hypothesis, which states that there is a direct effect of Task Complexity on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, is not accepted (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438.

Thus the hypothesis (H7) is rejected 0.09 at a T-value of 1.807 which is small from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.421. Thus the hypothesis, which states that there is a direct effect of Task Complexity on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, is not accepted (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438. Thus the hypothesis (H7) is rejected 09 at a T-value of 1.807 which is small from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.421. Thus the hypothesis, which states that there is a direct effect of Task Complexity on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, is not accepted (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438. Thus the hypothesis (H7) is rejected; thus, the hypothesis, which states that there is a direct effect of Task Complexity on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, is not accepted (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438. Thus the hypothesis (H7) is rejected; thus, the hypothesis, which states that there is a direct effect of Task Complexity on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, is not accepted (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438. Thus hypothesis (H7) is rejected (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438. Thus hypothesis (H7) is rejected (H5) is rejected. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.013 at a small T-value of 0.643 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.520. Thus the hypothesis (H6) is rejected. Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers through intervening Continuous Commitment with a Path Coefficient value of 0.054 at a small T-value

of 0.776 from the standard t-table of 1.96 and a P-Value of 0.438. Thus the hypothesis (H7) is rejected

Table 2: Test Results of the Model Structure

Variable	R-Square
Job Satisfaction + Task Complexity → Personal Values	0.514
Job Satisfaction + Task Complexity → Continuous Commitment	0.475

From the measurement table of the research model above, it can be explained that the effect of job satisfaction and task complexity on personal value produces an R-Square of 0.514, meaning that these two variables affect only 51.4% and the remaining 48.6% are influenced by other variables not tested in the study. This. For the structure of the second model, the effect of job satisfaction and task complexity on continuous commitment produces an R-Square of 0.475, meaning that these two variables affect only 47.5%, and the remaining 52.5% is influenced by other variables not tested in this study.

5. CONCLUSION

- a) From the study results, it can be concluded that Job satisfaction significantly affects the personal value of millennial workers, with a T-value of 2.647.
- b) Task Complexity significantly affects millennial workers' values, with a T value 4.724. Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers, with a T-value of 1.870.
- c) Task Complexity significantly affects the Continuous Commitment of millennial workers with a -T value of 8.594. Continuous commitment has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers, with a T-score of 1.807.
- d) Job satisfaction has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers by intervening with Continuous Commitment with a T-value of 0.643.
- e) Task Complexity has no significant effect on the personal value of millennial workers by intervening with Continuous Commitment with a T-value of 0.776.

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